

SOCIAL WORK AS A KIND OF SCIENTIFIC KNOWLEDGE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7479193>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 14th December 2022

Accepted: 23th December 2022

Online: 24th December 2022

KEY WORDS

Pedagogy, social, interdisciplinary, nature conformity, humanism, cultural conformity, efficiency.

ABSTRACT

In educational work with "special" children, the necessity and importance of rehabilitation and pedagogical knowledge for a teacher in modern mass education, the formation of his culture as a rehabilitator and the possession of a certain positive quality of psycho-physiological and mental-spiritual state are substantiated. The article outlines possible ways that provide no less than "restoration of vital energy" of students and pupils and a real basis for self-realization in harmony with the world.

Social pedagogy is a system of knowledge about the pedagogical regulation of relations between the individual and the environment. As an independent branch of scientific pedagogical knowledge, social pedagogy integrates information about the system of purposeful social and pedagogical activity in a specific microenvironment in the interests of harmonizing the life and social relations of an individual.

The concept of "social pedagogy", proposed by the German scientist and teacher A. Diesterweg one hundred and fifty years ago (1850), has not yet had an unambiguous interpretation. As a theory and field of practice, social pedagogy is currently in the process of scientific development.

As a branch of integrative pedagogical knowledge, social pedagogy explores a special sphere of social reality in which socially and personally determined

activities are carried out, aimed at pedagogizing the sociocultural environment and regulating social relations.

Socio-pedagogical activity is the activity of the subject to transform the social situation in accordance with pedagogical goals and objectives.

Socio-pedagogical activity has an interdisciplinary character. It is closely connected with the economic, political and personal conditions of human life, with the state social policy, the communication capabilities of the individual in the social sphere.

Social Pedagogy in the System of Scientific Knowledge In the system of scientific knowledge natural, social (social, humanitarian) and technical sciences are singled out.

Social pedagogy is, in its essential content, a social science. However, the research carried out within its framework

is interdisciplinary in nature and is closely related to the natural sciences (medicine, physiology, biology), at the same time interacting with the complex of social sciences (philosophy, sociology, social work, jurisprudence, various branches of pedagogy and psychology, etc.).

Social pedagogy "enters into interdisciplinary contacts with the sociology of education, the sociology of education, pedagogical and social psychology, psychology. All this diversity of scientific knowledge is organized into a single theory thanks to the fundamental foundations on which any system of specific scientific knowledge, any science, is based. For social pedagogy, which is a complex multifunctional, multicomponent branch of public knowledge, the basic foundations are pedagogical science and practice.

The generally accepted list of pedagogical scientific disciplines that make up the structure of modern pedagogy and enter into interdisciplinary contacts with social pedagogy can be represented as follows.

Based on the fact that social pedagogy as a science is connected with a whole range of other sciences, and in terms of its structure, social pedagogical activity is a universal type of activity, several groups of principles of social pedagogy can be distinguished:

- general philosophical principles: determinism, reflection, development;
- general principles of social (social) sciences: historicism, social conditioning, social significance;

- the main specific principles of social pedagogy: integrity, conformity to nature, humanism, cultural conformity.

The classification of the principles of social pedagogy is based on the identification of the most important factors that determine the effectiveness of socio-pedagogical activities in regulating the relationship between the individual and the environment.

The principle of integrity reflects the relationship of social education with other factors that determine the development of the child. It substantiates the process of harmonious development of man as a biosocial and existential being. The principle of integrity in social pedagogy means achieving the unity of all conditions that ensure the effectiveness of the social development of the individual:

1) designing the socio-pedagogical process and educational relations on the basis of a personality-oriented approach to the development of each pupil;

2) the use of an interdisciplinary approach based on the integration of different areas of scientific knowledge;

3) the use of the development potential of the child and the capabilities of a particular microcommunity in the course of the socio-pedagogical process, the timely adjustment and transformation of educational means to achieve the ultimate goal of education.

The implementation of the principle of integrity contributes to the ordering of the socio-pedagogical process.

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